

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Abca6.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Abca6 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Kaminski, W.E., Wenzel, J.J., Piehler, A., Langmann, T. and Schmitz, G., 2001. ABCA6, a novel a
12 subclass ABC transporter. Biochemical and biophysical research communications, 285(5), pp.1295-1301.